

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OCCHIUTO****FIRST NAME: VALERIO****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (Microsoft Word 2022 per Microsoft 365 MSO on Windows 10 Pro)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text:

1. The Writing Process (**Sebranek, Meyer, and Kemper 1990, 12-27**)
2. Essay writing (**EUCLID 2024, 7**)
3. Rules of thumb (**EUCLID 2024, 12-14**)
4. Building paragraph (**Sebranek, Meyer, and Kemper 1990, 75-89**)
5. Chicago Rule of Style (**EUCLID 2024, 44-50**)
6. Plagiarism (**EUCLID 2024, 33-39**)

A QUICK GUIDE TO BUILD A DISSERTATION

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D period one outlines an overview of the research and thesis dissertation process, covering key principles and basic rules to support doctoral students in proper academic writing skills. The course plans to study and interact with two educational books and four online video lessons, supplemented with several helpful documents to utilize as checklists or sample templates.

Among those precious materials, the *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999) constitutes a valuable guide for non-native English language speakers, offering a comprehensive overview of the writing process by distinguishing structure, essential elements, and different styles. Differently, the *ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack* (EUCLID 2024), revised by Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma, delves deeper into academic writing, focusing on crafting academic essays with correct punctuation and appropriate rule of style (Chicago) with references to other styles. Additionally, the video lessons provide guidance on using tools such as *Grammarly Tutorial: Making Use of Grammarly Premium & An Overview of Grammarly for Google Docs* (Roshan 2018) and *How to Use Zotero: A Complete*

Beginner's Use (Bardburn 2022) to ensure proper grammar and academic referencing in line with EUCLID's formal and substantial guidelines.

As expected, academic writing should not be considered an improvised task. Research and dissertations require careful planning, structure, and attention to detail to maintain scientific rigor. Beyond technical skills, this process demands further soft skills such as profound goodwill, strong perseverance, and an excellent psychophysical balance. Moreover, writing should be viewed as a creative endeavor: a form of art that engages the writer's mind in a dynamic process of intellectual discovery.

2) THE WRITING PROCESS

To frame the discussion, it is essential to clarify that this analysis pertains to professional writing, which adheres to a structured and scientific methodology. In this perspective, professional writing is a process characterized by four different steps, without prejudice to the possibility of taking a step forward to develop a better idea or, in case, a step backward for making corrections or adjustments:

a) **selecting** refers to the process of choosing a subject to explore in writing (Sebranek, Meyer, and Kemper 1990, 12). Disserting a thesis requires the capacity to uncover and deepen new nuances of an argument, even on topics that have already been studied. Locating an interesting topic requires awareness and intuition. However, at this stage, having a general idea is sufficient.

b) **collecting** refers to all the searching, gathering, thinking, talking, and planning that goes on during a writing project (Sebranek, Meyer, and Kemper 1990, 12). I consider this the most interesting moment due to the pleasure of opening my mind while reading and learning new arguments. Techniques such as brainstorming, clustering, and writing freely on paper can help to narrow the focus. Consequently, once sufficient ideas have been gathered, these should be analyzed and organized into a structured plan to serve as the foundation for the entire work. There are different ways to develop this plan, such as drafting a list, a brief outline, or a cluster; personally, I used to apply all of them randomly.

c) **connecting** refers to all the writing you do to connect and shape your thoughts into a meaningful composition (Sebranek, Meyer, and Kemper 1990, 12). In my experience, this is the most creative step, but being a non-native English speaker is also the most challenging moment. I usually begin it with an open-minded so that the draft can maintain an original path; then, once the draft has been thrown down and left apart for some days, I proceed to revise it by reviewing the main picture, checking paragraphs and sentences, adding or cutting detailed information, and finally rechecking the entire paper with a broad overview.

d) **correcting** refers to those finishing touches that are made as the writing is put into its final form (Sebranek, Meyer, and Kemper 1990, 12). It represents the final step, the final touch before the script becomes part of a broader and complex world of knowledge, and concerns spelling, punctuation, capitalization, usage, and grammar. On the assumption

that substance appears inadequate without a precise form of presentation (especially in the academic environment), I conclude the dissertation by respecting a high level of precision, and so I revise it, ensuring that the work adheres to professional standards.

3) ESSAY WRITING

This chapter overlaps what EUCLID appropriately pretends by its doctoral students with Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer's criteria, further with my own experiences in thesis dissertations, while offering a **valuable and practical guide for beginners**.

The pyramid model illustrated in the *ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack* (EUCLID 2024, 7) provides a summary roadmap to whom the student should refer in disserting a thesis. It begins with analyzing the research question, defining key terms, and establishing the point of view, corresponding to Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer's "selecting phase." Then, it emphasizes using credible academic sources, namely scientific publications and authoritative documents, while taking notes about the main concepts extracted (EUCLID 2024, 7), referable to Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer's "collecting phase." The *ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack* (EUCLID 2024) also plans to structure the draft into three main parts: introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 9), referable to Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer's "connecting phase." Lastly, referring to what Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer indicate as the "correcting phase," EUCLID's pyramid suggests discussing the draft with peers only after revisions.

Having carried out multiple theses, I could not disagree with this well-structured methodology, except that I tend to integrate reference-checking into the editing process rather than postpone it until after peer feedback. However, this approach ensures that citations are accurate and complete, regardless of external suggestions.

4) RULES OF THUMB

EUCLID correctly recommends abiding by **some practical rules in drafting**. Papers should critically assess some important aspects of one of the theories we have discussed and must not try to provide a comprehensive overview of the theory (EUCLID 2024, 12).

Though any scientific publication includes a preliminary chapter called literature overview, which exposes the argument research status at that moment, this ensures the dissertation focuses on advancing new insights. Avoiding generalizations is another key recommendation, as overly broad conclusions can dilute the clarity and impact of the research. A focused, precise argument is essential to producing meaningful academic work.

One effective strategy is to "argue against yourself" when making criticisms (EUCLID 2024, 13). Following Hegelian dialectics, this process involves presenting a thesis and its antithesis and ultimately synthesizing the two. This practice fosters intellectual rigor and deepens the research process.

I firmly believe that questioning ourselves and our thoughts is the precursor to developing the human being's essence; hence, it could not be different for a doctoral dissertation. In my opinion, arguing against ourselves is a clear and ongoing intelligence symptom.

5) BUILDING PARAGRAPH

Entering the draft's structure, we should intend the paragraph as a unit of writing that is easy to control (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 75) or otherwise, such as a **microsystem contained within a bigger one** (which is the essay). Not by chance, I consider it appropriate to carry out a parallelism between them.

Like an essay, a paragraph consists of three parts: the controlling sentence introduces the topic and guides the development of ideas; the body contains detailed information supported by at least two or three sentences; the closing sentence summarizes the paragraph and reinforces its main idea.

The book also outlines different ways to structure paragraphs, including chronological order, cause, and effect, or comparison and contrast (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 77). While these guidelines are helpful, creativity is crucial to engaging the writing.

6) CHICAGO STYLE

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 41). EUCLID's adoption of the Chicago style provides a standardized framework for academic work.

While some may view these rules as restrictive, they are **tools that facilitate the clear communication of ideas**. For instance, they standardize how foreign words are introduced or how emphasis is added through italics (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 47). These "micro rules" are indispensable for producing polished, professional work.

Even though it seems like a subtopic in the dissertation process, thanks to EUCLID, I have learned the importance of respecting those micro rules that will accompany me on a unique learning path that will last a lifetime.

7) PLAGIARISM

During a plurennial lower academic course, I frequently heard about avoiding plagiarism. Still, with intellectual honesty, I did not yet know the cases in which a scholar could get in trouble.

Erroneously, I believed it consisted of the prohibition of literally copying from third-party sources. Now I understand that plagiarism is not just copying words but also **taking on someone's ideas**, such as paraphrasing without crediting the author (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 34). For instance, in my previous conception, I would not have referenced the last sentence, assuming that the phrase was somehow different compared to the original one.

What I have learned entails an internal change in my brain. I now recognize the need for a deeper understanding of plagiarism and its consequences to prevent accidental violations. Reflecting on my earlier work, I appreciate the role of professors in ensuring academic integrity.

8) CONCLUSION

Looking at what is written within the draft in bold makes it possible to understand what I think the *ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack* (EUCLID 2024) aims to introduce, as follows: the writing process can be distinguished into four phases; this paper offers a valuable guide for beginners supplemented with some practical rules in drafting; the paragraph is a microsystem contained within a bigger one; the Chicago Rule of Style provides tools that facilitate the clear communication of ideas; plagiarism means taking someone's ideas.

To be honest, I have not had the chance to clarify the difference between US and UK spelling due to the lack of discursive text in the corresponding chapter. However, understanding the significance, I engage myself to develop the argument better to avoid future mistakes. Likewise, thanks to EUCLID, I recognize the importance of communicating clear ideas and how valuable it is to have a method. Earlier, I did not know what *Zotero* and *Grammarly* were; now, I have added these tools to my suitcase, and I look forward to utilizing them throughout the doctoral course.

REFERENCES

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